

Recommended citation: Schmitt, F. J., Schröder, C., Campbell, Z. Y., Wilkening, S., Moldenhauer, M., & Friedrich, T. (2017). Self-Dependent Students in Transdisciplinary Projects Tend to Higher Interest in Sustainability Research. In Quadrado, J. C., Bernardino, J., & Rocha, J. (Eds.), *Education Excellence for Sustainability. SEFI 45th Annual Conference* (pp. 25-32). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Azores, Portugal. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14697967.

Self-dependent students in transdisciplinary projects tend to higher interest in sustainability research

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ABSTRACT

The orientation program MINT^{grün} at Technische Universität Berlin (TU Berlin) offers two study semesters for open choices of teaching modules including a series of specially designed laboratories for research-based learning (RBL).

The online project laboratory in chemistry (OPLChem) offered in MINT^{grün} follows the concepts of RBL with a transdisciplinary approach and allows for a free choice of a project drafted by the students themselves. The concept of the OPLChem seems to motivate the students to follow their interests in sustainability research as during the last two years 16 of 23 student groups chose topics typically related to sustainability. Our students publish their results in the form of videos and blogs in the internet. In this way a growing pool of new blogs and online videos of various experiments was established for the public.

Conference Key Areas: Sustainability and Engineering Education, Open and Online Engineering Education, Attractiveness of Engineering Education

Keywords: research based learning, project laboratory, sustainability research

INTRODUCTION

Topics related to sustainability research motivate students in the initial stage of their studies. The orientation program MINT^{grün} offered as a two semester program at TU Berlin helps students to discover interests before entering a graduation course [1].

Especially during the initial phase of studies there is a lack of student centred learning environments in most STEM courses (German: MINT for Mathematics, Informatics, Nature Sciences and Technics). In contrast to this MINT^{grün} offers nine specially designed, interactive laboratories which cover topics such as robotics, construction, environmental research, mathematics, gender studies and chemistry. The suffix “grün” which means “green” indicates the link to sustainability and is intended to motivate the students’ interest in this area at the initial stage of their studies.

The students choose at least one laboratory where they have an interest to conduct their own project. The topics are often related to contemporary research topics in ecology, sustainability or social and intercultural debates and therefore of high societal interest. In the framework of MINT^{grün} we offered the Online Project Laboratory in Chemistry (OPLChem).

The OPLChem follows the concepts of research-based learning (RBL) with free choice of research topics and a transdisciplinary approach; the latter is a key component of sustainability science [2, 3]. It was reported in literature that free-choose learning and research promotes environmentally sustainable attitudes and behaviour [4].

In recent years students chose 16 out of 23 projects directly related to sustainability research such as the quantification of heavy metals in drinking water, in nutrition supplements, in food and soil; the production and decay of biodegradable plastics, electricity from bacteria, fuel cells, hydrogen from bacteria, photosynthesis research and alternatives for industrial fertilizers.

The concept of the OPLChem further motivates the students by giving them the opportunity to present their results to the public. The students produce online-videos and publish blogs in the internet.

The growing pool of online materials represents another aspect of sustainability as the experimental results are more persistently visible in comparison to the usually written paper protocols that vanish after correction by the supervisors. Videos turn out to be a suitable tool explaining important aspects of the theory, the configuration of complex experimental setups, the basic questions of interest and finally the videos offer a presentation tool for the students [5, 6].

In 2013 Professor Thomas Friedrich was awarded a Fellowship by the Joachim Herz Foundation for excellence in teaching, specifically for the whole teaching concept of the OPLChem. One year later, in 2014, Franz-Josef Schmitt was awarded a Fellowship by the Joachim Herz Foundation for excellence in teaching with regards to the targeted inversion of internships in chemistry, biotransformation and micro economy (IGT-educationTUB).

1. CONCEPT OF RESEARCH-BASED LEARNING AND MINT^{GRÜN}

MINT^{grün} students are school absolvents that just entered university typically aged 18 years or even younger [1,7]. RBL trains skills such as the ability to independently formulate questions and conceive research plans and to take responsibility for the outcome of projects [8]. The connection of orientation studies and RBL seems to be most promising in achieving successful identity, orientation and self-confidence among the students [9,7]. Interestingly it also activates students to choose topics related to sustainability [3]. RBL is additionally well suited for online support and new technologies as part of blended learning concepts [10,11].

2. THE ONLINE PROJECT LABORATORY IN CHEMISTRY (OPLCHEM)

The OPLChem follows the concept of RBL. Team RBL is a very effective way of promoting students' awareness of social, economic and environmental sustainability issues [12]. The introduction period of the OPLChem (see Fig. 1) mainly divides into i) the best practice examples introduced by students from former semesters (as part of their presentation) motivating the students research questions, ii) the investigation period for studying existing literature and collecting information and iii) the conception period combining ideas to an experimental concept, defining methods and considering the setup. Also the necessary materials are identified and organized. Usually the students define their topics within the first 2-3 weeks of the semester and come together in groups ranging from 2-4 participants. Then they conduct their research in the laboratory during the experimental period.

Fig. 1 Structure of the OPLChem in form of a gantt chart

At the end of the course the students have to present a written protocol and produce either a video or a blog where the conducted experiment and the results are described. Usually the video and blog are hosted at YouTube® or Wordpress®, respectively, and therefore public. Their presentations are impulse talks for the next group of students.

Fig. 1 presents the structure of OPLChem and the three overlapping periods which are marked in blue: 1) the introduction period, 2) the experimental period and 3) the presentation period. Marked in red one can see the segmentation of the introduction period and the presentation period. The semester change between March and April is indicated by a black vertical line.

3. RESULTS

During the last winter semester WS 2016/17 38 students participated in the OPLChem. The projects chosen by these students were: 1) oxygen production in photosynthesis, 2) light driven adaption of algae, 3) heavy metals in food supplements, 4) mercury in seafood, 5) gene analysis with polymerase chain reaction, 6) genetically modified organisms, 7) electricity produced by bacteria, 8) biopolymers, 9) generation and photocatalytic activity of nanoparticles, 10) optical properties of different nanoparticles and 11) function of ink erasers.

In recent years an average of about 50 % of all students who had undergone the OPLChem finished their projects with a presentation, written protocol and either video or online blog or both. All blogs as prepared by the students are collected in a metablog which is accessible via the URL <http://oplchem.wordpress.com> (Fig. 2)

Fig. 2 Metablog subsuming the students' efforts in the OPLChem

PROJEKT BOKUNSTSTOFFE

WIE NACHHALTIG SIND BOKUNSTSTOFFE WIRKLICH?

STARTSEITE • PROTOKOLLE • VIDEOS • ÜBER

POLYMILCHSÄURE

HERSTELLUNG VON POLYMILCHSÄURE

7. Februar 2017

Materialien

- Reagenzglas
- Laborwaage
- Bunsenbrenner

Video zur Durchführung

Beobachtung

L(+)-Milchsäure ist eine klare Flüssigkeit, Zinn(II)-chlorid ein feines, weißes Pulver. Durch das Erhitzen der Edukte in der leicht rauschenden Brennerflamme löst sich das Zinnchlorid zunächst. Im Laufe der 15-minütigen Reaktionszeit tritt unter starker Rauchentwicklung eine deutliche braune Verfärbung des Reaktionsgemisches auf. Nach dem Überführen in eine im Eisbad gekühlte Metallschale wird das zuvor flüssige Produkt zähflüssiger und erstarrt schließlich, wobei sich eine gelblichbraune, leicht klebrige Masse ausbildet.

Erklärung

D-Milchsäure

L-Milchsäure

Ausgangsstoff zur Synthese von Polymilchsäure ist die L(+)-Milchsäure. Sie trägt jeweils eine OH-Gruppe und eine COOH-Gruppe.

Reagieren zwei Milchsäuremoleküle miteinander, so wird die Hydroxylgruppe eines Milchsäuremoleküls unter Wasserabspaltung mit der Carboxylgruppe eines zweiten Milchsäuremoleküls zu einem Lactid verbunden.

Fig. 3 Screenshot of the blog <https://projektbiokunststoff.wordpress.com/>

Fig. 3 presents the screenshot of a group that synthesized and investigated a number of various biopolymers such as polylactic acid, polyhydroxybutyrate, galalith or starch. They compared these polymers with industrial biopolymers such as technically produced polylactic acid and the synthetic polymer polyurethane. The degradation in contact to earth and water as well as the solubility in various different solvents was studied. The findings were subsumed in a protocol as well as presented on the blog. For the synthesis of most of the biopolymers a short video was produced and linked to the blog. The students' presentation and discussion of their project can also be found on the blog.

4. DISCUSSION

The orientation study program MINT^{grün} is very successful regarding the number of participating students. The number of MINT^{grün} students rose from 77 in the first year, to 177 in the second year, to 325 in the third year and has stabilized at around 500 students since 2015. The proportion of women increased from 22% to 34% in the same time. In the winter semester 2015/16 21 students participated in the OPLChem. This number grew to the maximum capacity of 38 places in 2016/17: 28 students from Mint^{grün} and 10 students from Bachelor of Chemistry studied in the OPLChem during the winter semester 2016/17, of which 12 students were women (32 %). About 1/3 of the students from MINT^{grün} in the OPLChem announced an interest in continuing with Bachelor of Chemistry.

In general MINT^{grün} helped a lot of students to choose their future studies whereby most of the students who wanted to study announced that they are interested in STEM (up to 75%) [9].

We assume that for most of the students especially in the early stage of their studies there exists a strong attraction to topics of sustainability and the students appear to be highly motivated in getting engaged in such topics.

The concept of the OPLChem seems to motivate the students as they can follow their interests and have the opportunity to publish their projects in the form of videos and on a blog in the internet. Such online materials are transdisciplinary and sustainable as the students online published experimental results are more persistently visible in comparison to the usually written paper protocols that vanish after correction by the supervisors.

This approach also opened the laboratory for the public and turned out to be an interesting concept to support collaborations as for example with the office for urban development of the government of Berlin.

Interviews with the students showed that especially the groups who had experience with RBL during their school time were quick in finding project ideas or even wanted to proceed with their former school projects.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The main aim of the OPLChem is to introduce students to situations of real laboratory research and they should be motivated for hard working engagement to solve difficult issues in chemistry. This might sound as a contradiction to develop own interests however we believe that RBL can offer both, experience of reality and identification.

It turned out that this concept of RBL is highly appreciated by the students. Especially the flexibility in scheduling the time for the experiments was positively judged.

We believe that the concept of RBL in orientation studies together with transdisciplinarity for example by blended learning elements such as online videos and blogs is highly attractive and motivates sustainability research projects. RBL brings students into contact with the requirements of the subjects on the one hand and gives them freedom to follow own research questions on the other. It allows good students to explore their limits. RBL should ideally include elements which are typical for the subject such as the need to write elaborated and exact protocols as in studies of chemistry, so that the students in MINT^{grün} experience the study reality and get a good orientation from participating in OPLChem. But RBL should also allow for the freedom of a researcher to choose his questions, to design experiments and to schedule his time on his own.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge support by TU Berlin in the framework of the student reform project “educationZEN in Praktika”. Special thanks belongs to the board of teaching and studying (LSK) and the board of the faculty (FKR II) who were both engaged in discussions and contributed with constructive criticism to the success of this project and finally decided on the funding in a positive way. The authors thank the Executive Board (President Prof. Christian Thomsen and the Vice President for education Prof. Hans-Ulrich Heiss) from TU Berlin for his support to MINT^{grün}.

Thomas Friedrich and Franz-Josef Schmitt especially thank Stifterverband der Deutschen Wissenschaft and Joachim Herz Stiftung for supporting the projects “Onlineprojektlabor Chemie im Alltag” and “IGT- educationTUB” and support by the ministry of education and research (BMBF) for financing the *WIM^{plus}* project SynTUBio. Central institute of scientific cooperations (ZEWK) at TU Berlin is acknowledged for supervising *WIM^{plus}*.

Christian Schröder and Zulehya Yenice Campbell acknowledge support by the ministry of education and research (BMBF) for funding the project MINT^{grün}.

The authors thank Ahmad Aljanazrah from Bierzeit university Palestine for his support and didactic advices.

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